

Biochemical and Immunological Studies on the Effect of *Echinacea Purpurea* in Broilers

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Abstract

The objective of the present study was to evaluate the effect of feeding E.P on some biochemical and immunological parameters in broiler chicks. In this study, a total of 120 broilers were used and divided equally into 6 groups. Group (A) fed the normal basal diet. Group (B): were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P at a dose rate of 0.25 gm / kg diet. Group (C): were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P at a dose rate of 0.5 gm / kg diet. Group (D): fed the normal basal diet and challenged with *E. coli* O78 at 3 weeks old. Group (E): were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P at a dose rate of 0.25 gm / kg diet and challenged with *E.coli* O78 at 3 weeks old. Group (F): were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P at a dose rate of 0.5 gm / kg diet and challenged with *E.coli* 3 weeks old. Clinical signs, postmortem and mortality were recorded. Immune response and some biochemical parameters were measured. Serum total protein and globulin levels showed significance increase at 4th and 6th week in infected non-treated group. Albumin showed a decrease in the infected non-treated group at 6th week. ALT, AST, blood urea and creatinine levels showed increase in the infected non-treated groups at 4th & 6th week. Total cholesterol, triglycerides and LDL-C revealed a decrease in their levels with increased serum HDL-C in broiler at 4th & 6th week in the treated and infected treated groups. MDA level showed decrease in the treated and infected treated groups, meanwhile, SOD and GSH levels showed increase in the treated and infected treated groups at both 4th & 6th week. Results of IL-1 & IL-6 showed increase in the treated and infected non-treated groups at 4th & 6th week. Concerning with IgG level it showed a non-significant change in all groups at the 4th week, and a significant increase in the treated and infected non-treated groups at 6th week. Meanwhile, IgM level, showed a non-significant changes in the treated groups with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group at both 4th and 6th week.

Key Words: Echinacea Purpurea, Broilers, Biochemistry, Immune response.

Introduction

Phytobiotics are plant-derived natural bioactive compounds that can be incorporated into animal diets in order to enhance the performance and well-being of animals through the improvement of digestibility, nutrient absorption and elimination of pathogens residents in the animal gut (Muthusamy and Sankar, 2015). One of the most important phytobiotic and popular medical herb is *Echinacea purpurea* (E.P) (coneflower) (Barrett, 2003). This herbal medicine has been used from long time ago for a variety of purposes including treatment, growth enhancement and immunostimulation (Maisa and Fatma, 2014).

Echinacea and its different derivatives contain a variety of active substances like alkaloids, glycoproteins, polysaccharides, phenolic compounds, cinnamic acid, essential oil, hydrocarbons and flavonoids. These substances are effective in treatment of various ailments and proved to be beneficial in improving immunity (Landy et al., 2011). Echinacea was found to be a very potent antioxidant due to their contents of rosmarinic, cichoric acid and caffeic acid derivatives which are effective antioxidants in enhancement of free radical scavenging activity (Jahanian et al., 2017).

It has been reported that E.P has an interferon (IFN) like effect, activating macrophages and inducing the production of IL-1 and IFN.

Furthermore, E.P has been shown to have non-specific immuno stimulatory properties in vitro, including increased phagocytosis, increased cytokine production and natural killer cell activity (Dehkordi et al., 2011). Furthermore, Rahimi et al., (2011) mentioned that Coneflower (E.P) application increased production of such acute phase proteins as IL-1 and IL-6, or TNF- α - like substances. So, the present study aimed to: investigate the effect of supplementation of E.P in diet on broiler chickens on some biochemical blood parameters and on immune system in broilers either in healthy state or experimentally challenged with *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*).

Materials and Methods

1- Experimental chicks and treatment:

One hundred and twenty-one day old, apparently healthy Cobbs chicks were obtained from Ismailia/Misir poultry farm Ismailia city, Egypt. Chicks were housed in batteries and were divided into six equal treatment groups; each group include 20 birds reared for 6 weeks as the following:

Group A: chicks maintained as a control group without any treatment all over the experimental period and fed on commercial basal diet (served as control negative group).

Group B: were fed on commercial basal diet plus ethanolic extract of E.P (Immunovita capsules, EMA pharm pharmaceutical company, Egypt) continuously from one day old at a dose rate of 0.25 gm / kg diet all over the experimental period (Landy et al., 2011).

Group C: were fed on commercial basal diet plus ethanolic extract of E.P continuously from one day old at a dose rate of 0.5 gm / kg diet all over the experimental period (Landy et al., 2011).

Group D: chicks were challenged with 0.5 ml 24 hrs broth culture of field strain of *E. coli* (O78) serotype containing 4 x 10⁶ colony-forming units (CFU) by intranasal route at 3 weeks old and fed on commercial basal diet (act as control positive group).

Group E: were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P continuously from one day old at a dose rate of 0.25 g / kg diet all over the experimental period, chicks were challenged with 0.5 ml 24 hrs broth culture of *E.coli* (O78) serotype containing 4 x 10⁶ CFU by intranasal route at 3 weeks old.

Group F: were fed on commercial basal diet plus E.P continuously from one day old at a dose rate of 0.5 g / kg diet all over the experimental period, chicks were challenged with 0.5 ml 24 hrs broth culture of *E.coli* (O78) serotype containing 4 x 10⁶ CFU by intranasal route at 3 weeks old.

2- Sampling:

3 ml blood sample were collected in a plain tube from wing vein of the experimental chickens at the end of 4th and 6th week of age and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minute to obtain clear serum to be used for estimation of biochemical parameters and immunological studies.

3- Serum biochemical parameters:

Serum level of Total Protein, Albumin, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Creatinine, Urea, Cholesterol, Triglyceride, high density lipoprotein (HDL-C) and low density lipoprotein (LDL-C) were measured calorimetrically by using reagent test kits supplied by SPINREACT company- (Spain). Antioxidant assay were performed using commercial diagnostic kits for estimation serum level of Glutathione reduced (GSH), Superoxide dismutase (SOD) and Malondialdehyde (MDA) using Biodiagnostic kits, (Egypt). Serum level of globulin was calculated subtract the total serum protein from serum albumin (Joseph et al., 1972).

4- Immunological parameters:

Immunoglobulin G (IgG) and Immunoglobulin M (IgM) was determined using Elisa kits according to Larsson et al., (1993).

Interleukin 1 (IL-1 Beta) and Interleukin 6 (IL-6) were determined using Elisa kits according to **Wajant et al., (2003)**

5- Statistical analysis: The obtained data of the present study were analyzed statistically using one way analysis of variances (ANOVA) for all tested groups according to **Snedecor and Cochran (1989)**. Means separations were done by Duncan's Multiple Range test according to **Duncan (1955)**. The present data were analyzed using (SPSS, 20) for windows. Data were presented as mean \pm stander error (SE) and results were considered significant at probability level of 0.05 ($P \leq 0.05$).

Results

1- Clinical signs:

Experimentally infected non-treated chickens (group D) showed clinical signs of anorexia, ruffled feathers, dullness, depression, huddling together at 48 hrs post infection. While, after 3 days post infection, respiratory signs were developed in the form of rhinitis and wet eyes and rales. Necropsy finding of diseased chicks after one week post infection, showed several gross pathological lesions such as airsacculitis, severe lung congestion, pericarditis, perihepatitis with kidney and liver congestion and general signs of septicemia with mortality 25% (5/20). The birds experimentally infected and treated with E.P (groups E and F) displayed less clinical symptoms with the mortality rate 5 % in each group (1/20). The postmortem lesions were reduced to greater extent as compared to infected untreated birds. The severity of signs was reduced in all infected and treated groups than infected untreated ones.

2- Biochemical parameters:

In table (1): Proteinogram examination revealed a non-significant changes in total protein and globulin levels in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group at 4th

week, meanwhile at 6th week they have the same pattern of changes as they expressed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) as well as the infected non- treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. While the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a non-significant change when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week. Albumin level showed a non-significant change in the all treated groups when compared with the control healthy group at 4th week. Meanwhile, at 6th week it showed a non-significant change in the treated groups (B and C) when compared with the control healthy group. Meanwhile they expressed a significant reduction in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group, while the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant increase when compared with the infected non-treated group (D).

Biochemical analysis of the serum revealed that the activities of ALT and AST, blood urea and creatinine levels have the same pattern of changes as they expressed a non-significant changes in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile, the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant reduction when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at 4th and 6th week. Moreover, group (F) showed significant reduction than group (E) at 6th week only (Table, 1).

Table (2) showed a significant reduction in levels of Cholesterol, Triglycerides and LDL-C in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant reduction when compared with the infected non-treated group (D). Moreover, group (F) showed significant

reduction than group (E) at both 4th and 6th week. HDL-C level showed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant decrease in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant increase when compared with the infected non- treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week (Table, 2). Table (3) showed a significant reduction in MDA level at both 4th and 6th week in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant reduction when compared with the infected non- treated group (D). Moreover, group (F) showed significant reduction than group (E). SOD and GSH levels showed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant decrease in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant increase when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week (Table, 3).

3- Immunological results:

As shown in table (4), IgG showed a non-significant change between all treated groups

at 4th week. Meanwhile at 6th week it showed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) as well as in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group, while the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a non-significant changes when compared with the infected non-treated group (D). IgM showed a non-significant changes in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group at both 4th and 6th week, while the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a significant decrease when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th week. Meanwhile at 6th week, the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a non-significant change when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week (Table, 4). Both interleukin 1-Beta and interleukin 6 (IL-1 and IL-6) showed the same pattern of changes as they expressed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) as well as the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control healthy group. Meanwhile, the infected treated groups (E and F) showed a non-significant change when compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week (Table, 4).

Table (1): Effect of *E. purpurea* on some serum biochemical parameters of broiler chicks (means ± SE) on different groups.

	Parameters Groups	Total protein (gm/dL)	Albumin (gm/dL)	Globulin (gm/dL)	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	Urea (mg/dL)	Creatinine (mg/dL)
4 th week	Group A	4.33 ^d ± 0.15	2.7 ^a ± 0.05	1.63 ^b ± 0.19	14.4 ^c ± 0.7	78.7 ^c ± 2.09	10.60 ^b ± 0.22	0.4 ^c ± 0.01
	Group B	4.43 ^{cd} ± 0.07	2.7 ^a ± 0.07	1.66 ^b ± 0.14	14.2 ^c ± 0.1	79.4 ^c ± 1.45	10.40 ^b ± 0.26	0.4 ^c ± 0.01
	Group C	4.60 ^{bcd} ± 0.07	2.8 ^a ± 0.18	1.73 ^b ± 0.24	14.2 ^c ± 0.2	77.7 ^c ± 0.64	10.37 ^b ± 0.28	0.4 ^c ± 0.01
	Group D	5.10 ^a ± 0.05	2.7 ^a ± 0.07	2.43 ^a ± 0.07	19.7 ^a ± 0.6	97.1 ^a ± 1.58	12.17 ^a ± 0.12	0.8 ^a ± 0.04
	Group E	4.83 ^{ab} ± 0.14	2.8 ^a ± 0.18	1.98 ^{ab} ± 1.15	16.9 ^b ± 0.4	86.7 ^b ± 1.79	11.07 ^b ± 0.17	0.7 ^b ± 0.03
	Group F	4.77 ^{ab} ± 0.07	2.8 ^a ± 0.11	1.88 ^{ab} ± 0.08	15.8 ^b ± 0.3	79.4 ^b ± 1.18	10.57 ^b ± 0.48	0.4 ^c ± 0.03
6 th week	Group A	5.19 ^d ± 0.17	3.3 ^{ab} ± 0.12	1.86 ^c ± 0.28	20.8 ^c ± 0.7	75.9 ^c ± 1.86	11.43 ^c ± 0.88	0.5 ^c ± 0.02
	Group B	5.97 ^c ± 0.05	3.3 ^{ab} ± 0.05	2.67 ^b ± 0.02	21.7 ^c ± 0.5	76.7 ^c ± 1.24	11.1 ^c ± 0.26	0.5 ^c ± 0.02
	Group C	6.16 ^{bc} ± 0.17	3.4 ^a ± 0.09	2.73 ^b ± 0.11	20.2 ^c ± 0.7	76.4 ^c ± 0.45	10.90 ^c ± 0.28	0.5 ^c ± 0.01
	Group D	6.76 ^a ± 0.11	2.7 ^c ± 0.14	4.03 ^a ± 0.24	34.9 ^a ± 0.6	97.1 ^a ± 0.81	19.50 ^a ± 0.28	1.2 ^a ± 0.09
	Group E	6.53 ^{ab} ± 0.12	3.1 ^b ± 0.07	3.47 ^a ± 0.15	28.8 ^b ± 0.7	83.2 ^b ± 0.97	16.87 ^b ± 0.47	0.9 ^b ± 0.04
	Group F	6.69 ^a ± 0.11	3.1 ^b ± 0.12	3.63 ^a ± 0.10	22.2 ^c ± 0.7	71.9 ^c ± 1.7	11.53 ^c ± 0.17	0.6 ^c ± 0.01

Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at (P > 0.05).

Table (2): Effect of *E. purpurea* on serum lipid profile of broiler chicks (means \pm SE) on different groups.

	Parameters Groups	Cholesterol (mg/dL)	Triglycerides (mg/dL)	HDL-C (mg/dL)	LDL-C (mg/dL)
4 th week	Group A	181.40 ^b \pm 0.75	91.07 ^d \pm 0.43	37.57 ^{de} \pm 0.54	125.60 ^b \pm 1.39
	Group B	161.2 ^{de} \pm 1.9	87.72 ^e \pm 0.66	40.93 ^b \pm 0.64	102.30 ^{de} \pm 1.95
	Group C	156.90 ^e \pm 0.97	85.53 ^f \pm 0.32	44.00 ^a \pm 0.51	95.27 ^e \pm 0.94
	Group D	221.80 ^a \pm 3.02	115.80 ^a \pm 0.95	36.63 ^c \pm 0.48	162.00 ^a \pm 3.54
	Group E	170.7 ^c \pm 0.99	105.30 ^b \pm 0.58	38.53 ^{bcd} \pm 0.84	111.10 ^c \pm 0.21
	Group F	164.10 ^d \pm 1.34	98.73 ^c \pm 0.54	39.73 ^{bc} \pm 0.91	104.60 ^{cd} \pm 2.02
6 th week	Group A	147.00 ^c \pm 1.92	97.63 ^b \pm 1.26	40.73 ^b \pm 1.09	86.74 ^b \pm 1.05
	Group B	137.30 ^d \pm 0.78	89.17 ^c \pm 1.28	48.17 ^a \pm 0.58	71.27 ^c \pm 0.47
	Group C	134.40 ^d \pm 1.29	78.47 ^d \pm 3.22	47.53 ^a \pm 0.97	71.17 ^c \pm 2.02
	Group D	184.10 ^a \pm 1.69	131.60 ^a \pm 1.48	34.57 ^c \pm 0.78	123.30 ^a \pm 2.44
	Group E	156.20 ^b \pm 1.54	88.23 ^c \pm 1.35	46.20 ^a \pm 0.89	92.32 ^b \pm 0.43
	Group F	132.80 ^d \pm 1.29	83.53 ^{cd} \pm 1.49	48.77 ^a \pm 1.44	67.29 ^c \pm 2.11

Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at (P>0.05).

Table (3): Effect of *E. purpurea* on serum antioxidant activity of broiler chicks (means \pm SE) on different groups.

	Parameters Groups	MDA (nmol /ml)	SOD (U/ml)	GSH (mmol /L)
4 th week	Group A	9.23 ^d \pm 0.12	4.13 ^c \pm 0.14	0.47 ^b \pm 0.03
	Group B	7.17 ^e \pm 0.08	5.45 ^b \pm 0.05	0.55 ^a \pm 0.02
	Group C	5.30 ^f \pm 0.08	5.78 ^a \pm 0.03	0.57 ^a \pm 0.01
	Group D	19.66 ^a \pm 0.19	3.91 ^d \pm 0.13	0.41 ^c \pm 0.01
	Group E	12.69 ^b \pm 0.33	5.19 ^b \pm 0.09	0.48 ^b \pm 0.01
	Group F	9.95 ^c \pm 0.30	5.38 ^b \pm 0.08	0.53 ^{ab} \pm 0.02
6 th week	Group A	9.68 ^c \pm 0.08	4.41 ^b \pm 0.16	0.53 ^b \pm 0.01
	Group B	7.46 ^d \pm 0.06	5.74 ^a \pm 0.11	0.59 ^a \pm 0.01
	Group C	5.62 ^e \pm 0.07	5.96 ^a \pm 0.07	0.61 ^a \pm 0.01
	Group D	20.11 ^a \pm 0.87	3.92 ^c \pm 0.19	0.42 ^c \pm 0.02
	Group E	13.12 ^b \pm 0.29	5.61 ^a \pm 0.18	0.49 ^b \pm 0.03
	Group F	10.45 ^c \pm 0.28	5.93 ^a \pm 0.09	0.53 ^b \pm 0.02

Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at (P > 0.05).

Table (4): Effect of *E. purpurea* on some immunological parameters of broiler chicks (means \pm SE) on different groups.

	Parameters Groups	IgG (mg/dL)	IgM (mg/ dL)	IL-1 (ng/ml)	IL-6 (ng/ml)
4 th week	Group A	1.71 ^a \pm 0.06	0.87 ^b \pm 0.06	18.63 ^c \pm 0.13	140.66 ^c \pm 1.51
	Group B	1.67 ^a \pm 0.09	0.87 ^b \pm 0.03	20.10 ^b \pm 0.42	145.90 ^b \pm 1.73
	Group C	1.73 ^a \pm 0.12	0.90 ^b \pm 0.04	20.83 ^b \pm 0.35	148.2 ^b \pm 0.86
	Group D	1.80 ^a \pm 0.06	0.98 ^a \pm 0.06	26.03 ^a \pm 0.35	162.10 ^a \pm 1.89
	Group E	1.73 ^a \pm 0.03	0.89 ^b \pm 0.07	25.13 ^a \pm 0.20	158.20 ^a \pm 1.18
	Group F	1.67 ^a \pm 0.02	0.90 ^b \pm 0.01	25.66 ^a \pm 0.23	157.86 ^a \pm 0.90
6 th week	Group A	1.79 ^d \pm 0.02	0.92 ^d \pm 0.10	19.55 ^c \pm 0.12	145.11 ^c \pm 0.86
	Group B	2.13 ^c \pm 0.03	1.03 ^{cd} \pm 0.04	22.53 ^b \pm 0.36	152.83 ^b \pm 1.24
	Group C	2.27 ^{bc} \pm 0.08	1.05 ^{bcd} \pm 0.07	22.37 ^b \pm 0.57	153.22 ^b \pm 1.09
	Group D	2.76 ^a \pm 0.06	1.41 ^a \pm 0.07	28.17 ^a \pm 0.34	167.81 ^a \pm 2.27
	Group E	2.53 ^{ab} \pm 0.20	1.32 ^{ab} \pm 0.07	26.90 ^a \pm 1.09	164.51 ^a \pm 0.58
	Group F	2.67 ^a \pm 0.12	1.28 ^{abc} \pm 0.11	27.84 ^a \pm 0.23	166.54 ^a \pm 1.76

Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at (P > 0.05).

Discussion

The *E. coli* infected chicks showed anorexia, ruffled feathers, dullness, depression, huddling together at 48 hrs post infection. While, after 3 days post infection, respiratory signs were developed in the form of rhinitis and wet eyes and rales. No signs were recorded in the control group. Opacity and thickening of the air sac with presence of mild airsaccultis, perihepatitis and pericarditis were also observed during post mortem examination. Similar clinical signs and postmortem findings were reported by **Lisa (2013)**. In addition, less severe signs were observed in infected treated chickens (group E and F) with a decrease in mortality rate in comparison with *E. coli* infected group (D).

The results pointed out that chickens feed E.P in diet and experimentally challenged with *E. coli* developed less response in the form of clinical signs, morbidity and mortalities in comparison to infected non-treated group, this may due to inhibitory

effect of E.P in colonization of pathogenic *E. coli* which agreed with **Rahimi et al., (2011)** who found that feeding E.P in diet reduce the intestinal bacterial populations in broiler chickens. In the same context, the fighting ability of chickens against infection may be regard to immunostimulatory effects of and E.P which confirmed in immunological investigations in this study.

In the present study, analysis of blood samples reveled that all chicks treated with E. P showed a non-significant change in serum total protein levels and globulins at 4th week in compare with the control group that indicate no harmful effect of E.P on the liver. Meanwhile, the infected non-treated group with *E.coli* showed a significant increase of serum total protein and globulin levels at both 4th and 6th week, this in agreement with **Christie and Halliday (1979)**. Also there was a significant increase in treated groups at 6th week that indicates that E.P extract supplementation elevated the level of serum globulin, which acts as an

indicator of immune response and source of antibody (**Abdel-Fattah et al., 2008**) and immunoglobulins production.

Albumin measurements showed a non-significant change between all groups at the 4th week. Meanwhile at 6th week there were non-significant changes in the treated groups as compared with the control one was observed, meanwhile there were a significant reduction in the E.coli infected non-treated group was recorded, these results indicated hepatocellular damage due to infection as liver is responsible for the production of most of plasma protein (**Coles, 1986**). Meanwhile, all infected treated groups with E.P elicited a significant increase at 6th week as compared with infected non-treated groups. These results indicating improvements in hepatic functions because of hepatoprotective effect of E.P owing to the antioxidant effect of its higher contents of phytochemical compounds (**Maisa, M.G and Fatma, M.Y, 2014**).

The results of ALT and AST indicated a non-significant change in treated groups compared with the control healthy group at both 4th and 6th week that indicate safety usage of E.P which have no harmful effect on the liver. The infected non-treated group showed a significant increase in serum AST and ALT levels at both 4th and 6th week compared with the control healthy group which associated with hepatocellular damage in chickens as described by **Campbell and Coles (1986)**.

The E. coli infected broilers treated with E.P (E and F) denoted a significant decrease in serum AST and ALT values as compared with the infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week. These findings may be attributed

to the antioxidant effect of E.P as stated by **Zhai et al., (2007)** and **Nasir and Grashorn (2009)** due to their redox properties and chemical structure which can play an important role in neutralizing free radicals.

Blood urea and creatinine showed a non-significant change in the treated groups (B&C) at both 4th and 6th week that indicates that E.P has non-harmful effect on the kidney. While the E. coli infected non-treated chicks displayed a significant increase in both levels of blood urea and creatinine at both 4th and 6th week. These findings are in agreement with those of **Mellata et al., (2003)** who stated that avian pathogenic E. coli belongs to extra intestinal pathogenic group of E. coli which causes septicemia in poultry. Also, **Obrig et al., (1987)** concluded that an increase in blood urea and creatinine could be due to the effect of the microorganisms and its toxin on the kidneys. The results of lipid profile expressed a significant decrease in blood concentrations of total cholesterol, triglycerides and LDL-C in broiler chicks at 4th and 6th week of treatment in the treated groups with E.P (B&C) and in the infected treated groups (E&F), these results were in agreement with (**Bolukbasi et al., 2006 and Lee et al., 2009**). It has been reported that essential oils inhibit fatty acid synthetase complex, resulting in a reduction in serum triglycerides concentration (**Jahanian & Rasouli 2012**). In addition, supplemental E.P reduced serum cholesterol levels in the present study. It might be due to the inhibitory effect of bioactive components of Echinacea on β -hydroxy- β -methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase activity, a key enzyme in cholesterol biosynthesis (**Konjufca**

et al., 1997). Furthermore, Lee et al., (2009) mentioned that thyme oil as a component of E.P resulted in decreases in blood concentrations of triglycerides, LDL-C, and total cholesterol in broiler chicks. Meanwhile, the infected non-treated group (group D) showed a significant increase in blood concentrations of cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C and VLDL with a significant decrease in HDL-C level at both 4th and 6th week. These results agreed with those of Mekkawy, M.A. (2016) may be due to severe liver damage that leading to inadequate cholesterol utilization by liver leads to hypercholesterolemia.

Results of measurement of MDA level at both 4th and 6th week showed a significant reduction in the treated groups (B and C) when compared to the control healthy group (A), these in agreement with the results of Bayraktar et al., (2011) and Erdogan et al., (2005). They found that usage of an antioxidant additive in broiler diets could prevent the oxidative stress and decrease MDA as lipid peroxidation marker. Meanwhile level of MDA showed a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (D) when compared to the control group at both 4th and 6th week that may be due to stress. Results of measurement of SOD and GSH levels at both 4th and 6th week showed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C) when compared to the control healthy group. In agreement with our results, Magda K., (2011) recorded a significant increase in the activity of SOD in groups of male rats fed on E.P (30 mg/Kg body weight/day) and exposed to gamma radiation, this increase might be attributed to increased expression of this enzymes as a self- defense mechanism against oxidative stress. This could be attributed to the presence of echinacoside and caffeic acid in E.P which are potent scavengers of free

radicals. The infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week showed a significant decrease when compared to the control healthy group. Immunoglobulin results of the 6th week revealed a significant increase in IgG level in the treated groups (B and C) that due to potent immunostimulant effect of E.P. that improved serum immunoglobulin concentration, especially IgG concentration in a study conducted by Bohmer et al., (2008), also due to its activation effect to bone marrow in agreement with Zhai et al., (2007), infected non-treated group (D) also revealed a significant increase in IgG level when compared to the control healthy group as IgG production increase in a delayed response to infection that result agreed with Rehman et al., (1999). Meanwhile, IgM level showed a non- significant change in the treated groups (B and C) with a significant increase in the infected non-treated group (group D) when compared to the control healthy group as IgM is predominantly found in the lymph fluid and blood for neutralization of infectious agent in the early stages of disease and still in blood for (2-3) weeks post infection. Results of measurement of both interleukin (IL-1 β and IL-6) showed the same pattern of changes at both 4th and 6th week as they expressed a significant increase in the treated groups (B and C). These findings are in agreement with those of Rahimi et al., (2011) who mentioned that application of E.P in broilers increased production of such acute phase proteins as interleukin (IL-1 and IL-6). Also, Classen et al., (2006) attributed the increase of IL-6 production in broilers to be the consequence of a general activation of macrophages. The infected non-treated group (D) at both 4th and 6th week showed a significant increase when compared to the control healthy group. This in agreement with Nakamura et al., (1998) who mentioned that E. coli Lipopolysaccharide in chicks may induce the elevation of IL-6.

Reference

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